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PERSONALIZING INFLAMMATORY BOWEL DISEASE TREATMENT: THE EMERGING ROLE OF PHARMACOMICROBIOMICS

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Introduction: Pharmacomicrobiomics is rapidly emerging as a cornerstone of precision medicine in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). The aim of this study was to provide a comprehensive overview of the bidirectional interactions between gut microbiota (GM) and IBD pharmacotherapies.

Material & Methods: Data were obtained from articles published up to 2025. The research was performed using the following keywords: pharmacomicrobiomics, biotransformation, metabolism, ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease.

Results: The GM enzymatically activates key therapies such as sulfasalazine (azoreductases) and thiopurines (xanthine dehydrogenase). Bacterial metabolism can also deactivate or transform drugs (methotrexate to DAMPA), influencing efficacy and toxicity. Conversely, drugs shape the microbiota: 5-aminosalicylic acid enriches beneficial Firmicutes, corticosteroids alter microbial diversity and biologics increase short-chain fatty acids-producing taxa. Certain microbial signatures (*Faecalibacterium prausnitzii*, *Roseburia*) correlate with therapeutic response to biologics. Janus kinase inhibitors may contribute to the attenuation of adherent-invasive *Escherichia coli* colonization. Advancements such as organoid-microbiota co-cultures and integrated multi-omics are essential for identifying predictive microbial biomarkers. Incorporating GM profiling into clinical decision-making holds promise for improving outcomes. Targeted manipulation of the GM may open new avenues to enhance the efficacy of established therapies.

Conclusion: Pharmacomicrobiomics offers potential in the individualized therapeutic approach and also development of novel microbiome-guided treatment strategies.

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References

1. Becker HEF, Demers K, Derijks LJJ, Jonkers DMAE, Penders J. Current evidence and clinical relevance of drug-microbiota interactions in inflammatory bowel disease. *Front Microbiol.* 2023 Feb 23;14:1107976. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2023.1107976.
2. Lazarević S, Đanic M, Al-Salami H, Mooranian A, Mikov M. Gut Microbiota Metabolism of Azathioprine: A New Hallmark for Personalized Drug-Targeted Therapy of Chronic Inflammatory Bowel Disease. *Front Pharmacol.* 2022 Apr 5;13:879170. doi: 10.3389/fphar.2022.879170.
3. Oancea I, Movva R, Das I, Aguirre de Cárcer D, Schreiber V, Yang Y, Purdon A, Harrington B, Proctor M, Wang R, Sheng Y, Lobb M, Lourie R, Ó Cuív P, Duley JA, Begun J, Florin TH. Colonic microbiota can promote rapid local improvement of murine colitis by thioguanine independently of T lymphocytes and host metabolism. *Gut.* 2017 Jan;66(1):59-69. doi: 10.1136/gutjnl-2015-310874.